

Sample 14a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0278
{Si}	62.5
{Fe}	8.9
{Al, Si}	5.4
{Si, Ca LoP}	3.3
{Si, Fe}	2.6
{Al, Si, Ca}	2.3
{Al, Si, K}	1.9
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	1.8
{Ca}	1.6
{Na, Si, Cl}	1.1
{Cl}	1.1
{Mg, Si}	1.0
{Si, Ca HIP}	0.8
{Si, K}	0.6
{Cl}	0.6
{Si, S, Ca}	0.6
{Na, Al, Si}	0.6
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
{S, Ca}	0.4
{Si, Cl}	0.4
{Na, Si}	0.3
{Ca, Fe}	0.3
{Mg, Ca}	0.2
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
{Al}	0.1
{Zn-LA1}	0.1
{S}	0.1
{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.1
{Si, Fe}	0.0
{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.0
{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.0
{Si, P, Ca}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.2
Pellet	4.7
Ore preparation undifferentiated	1.8
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.3
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	6.7
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.2
Olivine flux	0.6
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.5
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	14.6
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.0
Carbon rich - other	2.7
Cement or BOF converter	0.2
Cement	1.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.2
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	55.2
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	9.6
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.1
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.2

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	6.6
Site - ore / hot metal	0.3
Site - slag	6.8
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.8
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.5
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	14.6
Site - carbon-rich other	1.0
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	2.7
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.2
Urban	1.4
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	55.2
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	9.6
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.3

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 14b

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0050
	{Si}	73.2
	{Fe}	6.5
	{Al, Si}	3.6
	{Ca}	2.5
	{Al, Si, K}	2.3
	{Cl}	1.7
	{Si, Fe}	1.5
	{Mg, Si}	1.2
	{Na, Si, Cl}	1.1
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.1
	{S, Ca}	0.5
	{Cl}	0.5
	{Si, K}	0.5
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.5
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.5
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.4
	{Na, Si}	0.4
	{Si, Cl}	0.3
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{S, Fe}	0.1
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Ca}	0.1
	{Al}	0.1
	{S}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg}	0.0
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.0
	{Si, Fe}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	1.5
Ore preparation undifferentiated	2.8
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.8
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.7
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.9
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.7
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	18.7
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.7
Carbon rich - other	3.8
Cement or BOF converter	0.1
Cement	0.7
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	64.5
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	3.0
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	4.3
Site - ore / hot metal	0.8
Site - slag	0.8
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.9
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.7
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	18.7
Site - carbon-rich other	0.7
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	3.8
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.1
Urban	0.8
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	64.5
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	3.0
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 14c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0044
	{Si}	68.9
	{Fe}	4.0
	{Al, Si}	3.4
	{Cl}	3.2
	{Ca}	3.0
	{Cl}	1.8
	{Si, P}	1.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.5
	{Si, Fe}	1.4
	{Al, Si, K}	1.3
	{Na, Si, Cl}	1.1
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.1
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.0
	{Mg, Si}	0.9
	{S}	0.8
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.6
	{Si, Ca HIP}	0.6
	{P}	0.6
	{Si, Cl}	0.5
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{Na, Si}	0.4
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.3
	{Al, Si, P}	0.3
	{Mg, Ca}	0.1
	{S, Ca}	0.1
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.1
	{S, Cl}	0.1
	{Al}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.5
Pellet	0.9
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.6
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.3
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.7
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.8
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	10.9
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.5
Carbon rich - other	4.8
Cement or BOF converter	0.8
Cement	3.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	60.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	8.7
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.7
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	1.7
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	1.2

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	2.0
Site - ore / hot metal	0.3
Site - slag	2.8
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.8
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	10.9
Site - carbon-rich other	0.5
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	4.8
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.8
Urban	3.2
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	60.1
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	8.7
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.7
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	2.9

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels